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BETWEEN SHARIA, CONSTITUTIONALISM AND HUMAN RIGHTS IN NIGERIA

OLUGBEMI FATULA

Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile - Ife, Nigeria
and

K. ADEYEMO

Osun State College of Technology, Esa - Oke

Introduction

With the swearing in of the Governors in their respective states, the Governor and the House of Assembly of each state became partners in the law making process and the judiciary maintains the role of interpreting the laws. Some of the elected governors of the northern part of Nigeria felt the need to put in place appropriate laws in accordance with the ethos and values of Islam or to reflect their Islamic faith or in accordance with the teachings of Islam as enunciated by the Maliki school of Islamic jurisprudence. Interestingly, the governors took the enabling power to do this from the constitution.¹

Zamfara state was the first state in Nigeria to introduce Sharia Penal Code in Nigeria. Zamfara state is a predominantly Moslem state. Other states that are basically Moslem states in the Northern part of Nigeria have adopted the Sharia legal system especially with respect to criminal responsibility. The states include Kano, sokoto, Katsina, Bauchi, Niger, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna, Borno, Kebbi and Yobe states.² The Sharia law of Zamfara state usually cited as The Sharia Penal Code Law of Zamfara State 2000 came into operation on the 27th day of January 2000 having been signed into law by ' Alhaji Ahmed Sani, the Governor of Zamfara state.

¹ John Ademola Yakubu: *The Dialectics of Sharia Imbrologlio in Nigeria*. Damyaxs Law Books, 2003 at pp. 20 & 22.

² See THIS DAY, Vol. 8 No 2526 March 23, 2022 at p. 43

This paper examines the reintroduction of Sharia penal codes by some Northern States as it relates to the question of constitutionalism and human rights provisions under the 1999 constitution. The paper examines the concept sources and scope of Sharia and attempted to locate the position of Sharia within the Nigeria legal system. The paper equally examines the constitutionality of Sharia as well as the effects of Sharia penal code on human rights in Nigeria. The paper concludes that the reintroduction of Sharia by some states is constitutional notwithstanding section 10 of the 1999 constitution as it is within the legislative competence of the states, though some provisions of the States Sharia penal code are clearly outside states legislative competence, particularly those provisions touching on police, evidence and prison.

The Concept, Sources and Scope of Sharia

The Concept of Sharia

In Islamic legal terminology, Shariah means the path established by God³ for men to follow in order to succeed in all aspects of worldly and spiritual life. It is the path that ensures success in this world and salvation in the hereafter.⁴

As a comprehensive legal system within the framework of the Holy Quran, the divine source; its contents are not confined to a particular theme, but contain the foundations for the entire system of life, covering a whole spectrum of issues which range from specific articles of faith and commandments to general moral teachings, crime and punishment, personal and public law and a host of other private and social matters⁵.

Sources of Sharia

Shariah as a system of law has three sources namely: the Quran, Sunnah and Human Reasoning through Ijtihad. Quran is the revealed scripture to mankind by Allah through the Holy Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and constitute the primary source of

³ Hereinafter referred to as *Allah* (SAW)

⁴ Prof. Sayed H.A. Malik, Shariah: A Legal System and a Way of Life : being a paper in the book: Perspectives in Islamic Law and Jurisprudence, Essays in honour of Justice (Dr) Muritala Aremu Okumola (JCA) edited by M. Oloyede Abdul Rahman. NAMLAS publication . 2000 at p . 25

⁵ Ibid at p . 28

Shariah. Sunnah refers to the sayings, acts, directives and teachings of the same prophet, which elucidate, or interpret the Quranic codes for a better understanding. This prophetic Sunnah serves as a supplement to the primary source of the divine law⁶.

As the revealed scripture to mankind by Allah through Prophet Muhammad, the Quran is the main source of Shariah. It consists of some regulations and guidelines on human conduct. In the Quran, Allah may define a crime, and then prescribes a specific punishment or a number of alternative punishments. Where many penalties are prescribed for an offence, man is expected to make a good use of his intellect to choose an appropriate punishment. Where Allah defines an offence without prescribing any punishment man is also expected to determine appropriate punishment. Where penalties are prescribed by Allah, such are immutable and should never be amended by man⁷.

While there is unity of opinion among scholars as regards the divine nature of Quran, the main source of Shariah, they disagree on the divine nature of the Sunnah. Citing many Quranic references, those who disregard its divinity argue that Prophet Muhammad (SAW) was a human being and his acts and statements should not be regarded as divine⁸.

Supporters of the divine status for the Sunnah also cited many Quranic verses in support of their argument, particularly where Allah says that his Prophet, Muhammad (SAW) did not talk in vain and that his utterances had been divinely guided⁹.

From the advent of Islam to the end of the era of the rightly guided Caliphs (al-khulafa' al-Rashidum)¹⁰ the only two sources of Shariah were the Quran and the

⁶ Hon. Justice A.B Wali, OFR, An Introduction to Islamic Legal theory: M. Oloyede Abdul Rahman . ed . Ibid at p . 86

⁷ Prof. Musa A. Ajetumobi , The Efficacy of Islamic Penal Law in Crime Control in the Society : M. Oloyede Abdul Rahman , ed . Ibid at p . 250.

⁸ Ibid

⁹ Ibid . See Quran 53 , al Najm 3-4

¹⁰ Abu Bakr , Umar . Uthman and Ali

traditions of Muhammad (al - Hadith) and these two were the bases of dealing with all affairs. After the death of the Holy Prophet, the Quran and his tradition, though remained the two major sources of Shariah, the death of the Holy Prophet naturally terminated their prolongation¹¹.

As the Islamic empire rapidly expanded through conquest to incorporate races, cultures and environment of various kinds, novel jurisprudential problems arose for which there were no references in the Quran or the prophetic tradition. This situation necessitated the formation of Ijma and Ijtihad¹² as additional sources of Islamic law¹³. Ijma is the unanimity of all the learned Muslims of a particular age who have attained the rank of Ijtihad, the capacity for individual judicial interpretation upon a certain issue after the death of Muhammad. The fact is that whenever they were faced with a fresh Jurisprudential problem, Muhammed's immediate successors would summon a general meeting of well informed companions, most of whom were still then in Medina and having attained the unanimity of these people upon the jurisprudential solution, the problems were dealt with accordingly. Consensus was also established on interpretation of some of the texts of the Quran and the tradition and analogy from either of them. Matters upon which the unanimity of the companions was attained fall into two separate categories nainel : matters dealing with the fundamentals of Islam¹⁴

¹¹ Dr. Iyasa Ade Bello, *The Development of Ijma' In Islamic Jurisprudence*: M. Oloyede Abdul Rahman, ed. Ibid. at pp. 162-163

¹² Madkur Mos, *Manahij Al-ijihad Fi al-Islam Kuwait: Jami at al Kuwayt* 1973. p. 44 and Shalabi A. Tarkh Madkur Mos, *Manahij Al - Ijtihad Fi al - Islam Kuwait: Jami al Tashri al - Islami Wa Tarikh al- Nuzum al- Qada'nyah Fi al - Islami* Cairo: Maktabat al - Nahdah, 1976. pp. 24-25. Literally, Ijtihad means self - exertion to the utmost degree to acquire an object. As an Islamic juridical term. it is used for self exertion to the utmost to formulate a legal opinion on the basis of evidence gathered from the principles of Islamic jurisprudence, where no rule of law is laid down in the scripture. The lawyer who is qualified to practice Ijtihad is called a Mujtahid. The juridical terms Qiyasi Isthsan and Istislah and all that the word Ijtihad embraces in itself came later on.

¹³ The purpose of the latter was to meet the demand of those novel jurisprudential problems while that of the former was to stand as a substitute authority to that of the prophet who was no longer physically present.

¹⁴ That is (a) The testimony to the oneness of Allah and the prophethood of Muhammad, (b) Praying five times daily (c) Alms giving (Zakah) (d) Fasting during Ramadan and (e) Pilgrimage to Mecca.

and the principles of faith¹⁵ and those concerning the details and these fundamentals , interpretation of some texts of the Quran and the tradition and analogical deductions from the texts of both of these sources. While consensus of the first category was absolute and non of the companions or the Muslims after them, irrespective of their sect controverted it that of the second category is a focus of controversy¹⁶.

With further expansion of the Islamic conquests towards the end of the reign of Umar and during the reign of Uthman, some of the companions who used to participate in judicial consultations migrated from Medina to other areas of the Islamic empire. The result was that the attainment of unanimous opinion on issues became difficult and the companions faced with fresh problems, exercised personal juridical interpretation (ijtihad) individually or in small groups each in their new abodes. These phenomena on many occasions led to different conclusions. Again, a different peoples, environment, culture and past civilization of the conquered territories in which the companions lived also had their influence on the juridical interpretation and the method of its application. This led to more controversy. Ijma was however later reached among the various schools of thoughts on the major issues and the difference among them came down mostly to relatively minor points of law and ritual. Subsequent generation could not open up discussion on issues upon which Ijma has been reached in these early generations. Hence, individual interpretation (Al - Ijtihad) and the divergence of opinion therein were confined to the issues on which no Ijma had yet being attended. As this were gradually narrowed down through generations and most areas of juridical interpretation were minutely covered and even imaginary juridical problems were provoked and solved. The scholars of later generations where restricted to commenting and elaborating the theses that contain those legal decisions¹⁷.

¹⁵ That is (a) Allah (b) His angels (c) His revelations (hooks) (d) His prophets (e) The Day of Resurrection and (1) Predestination, all in general but not in details.

¹⁶ Dr. Iyasa Ade Bello Op. cit at p. 164

¹⁷ Ibid at p. 172.

Scope of Shariah¹⁸

Shariah as an Islamic legal system and a way of life has eight main branches. The first, Thadah (Worship) embraces Tauhid (Science of the unity of God), Salat (Islamic ritual prayers), Saum (Fasting), Zakat (poor rate) and Hajj (pilgrimage).

The second branch, Al - Ahwal al - Shakhsiyyah (Personal Law) comprises the law of Marriage, Divorce, Custody of Children, Determination of Paternity of Children, Guardianship of Children, Succession, Bequest, Will, Endowment and Disputes arising out of Gift.

The third branch, the Mu'amalat (Law of Transaction) covers definition of Property, Title, Possession, Contract, Sales, Hiring, Pledge, Trust, Mortgage, Partnership, Pre – emption etc.

The fourth, Ahkam Sultaniyyah (Sovereignty) covers the Duty of a Leader of a Community, the Responsibilities of a Citizen, Rule of Law, Citizenship, Human Rights and Laws relating to Public Administration.

The fifth is International Law, Diplomacy, Treaties and Arbitration.

The Akhaq constitutes the sixth branch and this involves Morals including duties which a person owes himself, members of his family, neighbours, animals and other creatures.

The seventh branch is Al - Adah (ethics) and the al - Qada which refers to Judicial Administration and Procedure Governing Appointments of Judges, the Discipline and Procedure in courts.

And lastly, Uqubat. This is the Islamic Criminal law which deals with crimes against Allah and their punishment. Hudud deals with crimes against fellow beings and their punishments. An examination of these branches will review Shariah as a comprehensive legal system and a universal way of life¹⁹.

¹⁸ Prof. Sayed II. A. Malik Op. cit at pp. 25-26

¹⁹ Ibid

The Position of Sharia in the Nigerian Legal System

Shariah has always been an essential element of the legal system of Northern Nigeria²⁰. When the British conquered the northern emirates they found that the emirates had a well organized and efficient judicial system and administration of justice under the sovereignty of each Emir. The Shariah laws which the British called "Muslim Law" was the prevailing law in both civil and criminal matters administered by the Emirs courts and Alkali courts. Dogarai performed the functions of the police²¹. The British left the local emir in their position of power and only exert control through the existing administrative and judicial structure. Existing courts of the Emirs and Alkalis were thus given official status in the new British colonial order in which the British resident had extensive powers to supervise and control the courts²². The British did not interfere with the civil aspects of Shariah at all. The prevalence of Shariah civil law and its application in area courts in the Northern states is the same as it has been since pre-colonial times except that the old Alkalis Courts are now known as Area Courts. Again, appeals from the area courts now goes to the Shariah Court of Appeal on Muslim personal law and the High Courts on all other Shariah matters. Thereafter, appeals go to the Courts of Appeal and finally to the Supreme Court from both latter courts. It is significant to note that whenever an Area Court decides a case on Shariah Law, then all the courts exercising appellate jurisdiction over the case including the Supreme Court are bound by the law to apply the Shariah law²³.

Thus, in adjudication of cases concerning marriage and its dissolution, family relations, guardianship of infants and all questions relating to Muslims Personal Law etc, the Area Courts apply Shariah law according to the Maliki School²⁴.

²⁰ Rudd Peter; *Islamic Criminal Law in Nigeria*. Spectrum. 2003 at p. 5

²¹ Hon. Justice Mohammed Bello: *Shariah In the Lights of Nigerian Constitution* : M. Oloyede Abdul Rahman. ed. Op. cit. at p. 64

²² Peter Rudd Op. cit at p. 6

²³ Hon. Justice Mohammed Bello Op. cit at pp. 65-66.

²⁴ Ibid

As regards Criminal Law, the Islamic Criminal Law of the Maliki School continue to be applied, like other systems of customary law. The British only interfered with and influenced its application only on those points that they regarded as being repugnant to natural justice, equity and good conscience. Except for the ban on mutilating penalties and stoning to death there were no British objections to the application of Islamic Criminal Law until the end of the 1940s. After that time, British interference was limited to capital offences and certain procedural rules²⁵.

Constitutionality of the Reintroduced Islamic Penal Codes

The question, whether or not the reintroduction of Sharia's criminal law in the Northern States with a Muslim majority is constitutional has been hotly debated and highly politicized. The 1999 constitution is not helpful in this regard as it consists of provisions some of which could be interpreted as approving its introduction and some as prohibiting it. The fact that the issue has become politicized and the fact that it can only be challenged in court by a person with locus standi, which in Nigeria, is interpreted rather strictly make it unlikely that the would be resolved the courts.²⁶

Arguments Against Re - introduction of Shariah

The opponents of the Shariah argued that the decision to incorporate it as a state legal code raises a number of human rights issues for Muslims and Christians alike and that these human rights issues dovetail with constitutional concern as Section 10 of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria states that:

"The government of the federation or of a state shall not adopt any religion as a state religion"

This according to the opponents of Shariah is generally understood to mean that neither the legislative power nor the executive power may in any way be used to aid, advance, foster, promote or sponsor a religion. If that is accepted, then a decision to incorporate Shariah as a state code by the Northern states is tantamount to the

²⁵ See Olisa Agbakoba, SAN and Obiora Obeagu. Shariah: Death Penalty and the Constitution: THIS DAY Tuesday, Sep. 17 2002 at pp. 34 & 40

²⁶ Rudd Peter op. cit

adoption of Islam as a state religion and therefore in conflict with Section 10 of the 1999 Constitution. According to these opponents of Shariah, Nigeria is a secular state. Secularity means that religion should not be permitted to enter into the functions of the state.

Secularity of state is a tool for safeguarding religious harmony and securing freedom of religion as guaranteed by section 38 of the 1999 constitution. Without secularity, religious ideologies tends to become oppressive and the foundations of religious tolerance are destabilized. Section 10 of the 1999 Constitution, which prohibits either the federal or state governments from adopting any religion as state religion is not without controversy for its ambiguity. The provision is quite wide. But the United States has a comparable provision, whose purport is similar to but narrower than Section 10 of 1999 Constitution. The first amendment to the US Constitution states that:

"Congress shall make no law respecting establishment of religion."

Comparative analysis of the language employed in both jurisdictions showed that section 10 of the Nigerian Constitution is a clearer, positive and aggressive prohibition of state religion than the US. What is required for a violation of section 10 of the 1999 Constitution to occur is the implementation of a measure or chains of measures that leads to the establishment of a state religion. It may be administrative, legislative or otherwise. But once there is a pointer to the fact that a particular religion is government religion, the legal effect would be that a state religion has been adopted²⁷.

Again, the opponents of Shariah have contended that the argument that Shariah is made for and applicable only to Muslims and cannot therefore be regarded as a state religion has not followed the matter to a logical conclusion. According to these opponents the test should be:

“If your religion allows you to drink beer but in Zamfara State, Shariah religion prohibits you from drinking beer,

²⁷ Ibid

thereby curtailing the freedom you have under your own religion, then Islam has become a state religion. It is immaterial that you may elect to be tried under the law. The fact is that you have being found guilty of an offence under the law of a religion which is not your religion”²⁸.

Arguments in Support of Shariah

The argument that Shariah Penal Codes conflict with section 10 of the 1999 Constitution has been challenged by some Muslim jurists and politicians especially those from the North. They rightly argued that Shariah has been an integral part of Northern Legal system up to 1960. Its reintroduction does not amount to the adoption of a state religion, as it applies only to Muslims and not to Christians. The general part of the Shariah codes state those who are amenable to the jurisdiction of this court. The Zamfara state Penal Code Law 2000 in its general part provides that:

“every person who professes the Islamic faith and/or every other person who voluntarily consents to the exercise of the jurisdiction of any of Shariah Courts (Administration of Justice and certain consequential changes) Law, 1999, shall be liable to punishment under the Shariah Penal Code for every act or omission contrary to the provisions thereof of which he shall be guilty within the state“.

Certain consequences follow from this provision. First, this law is not general in its application. It relates only to those who profess the Islamic faith. By this law therefore, the operation of the Shariah law in Zamfara state like in other states that have followed suit has become a personal issue. It applies only to those who profess the Islamic faith. The Shariah Law of Kano state 2000 is even more specific in this regard. Section 5 of the Shariah Law of Kano state, 2000 provides thus:

²⁸ Ibid

"5(1) Subject to the provisions of the schedule to this law, the court shall in addition to such other jurisdiction as may be conferred upon them by a law of the state and subject to the provisions of the Constitution exercise original jurisdiction in all civil and criminal matters.

(2) The Shariah Court shall have jurisdiction to hear and determine civil matters and causes where all the parties are Muslims.

(3) The Shariah Court shall also have jurisdiction to hear and determine criminal cases where the accused person is a Muslim.

(4) Where only one of the parties to a civil cause or matter is a Muslim, the Shariah Courts shall not have jurisdiction to hear and determine the cause or matter, unless where the non - Muslim submits to the jurisdiction in writing.

(5) Where one or more of the several persons are non Muslims and the non - Muslims refuse to submit to jurisdiction, the Shariah Court shall not have jurisdiction to hear and determine the case. But the court shall have the power to try the Muslims, and refer the case of others to Magistrate Court, or such other court with competent jurisdiction to try the offence(s).

Secondly, the interpretation of section 10 1999 Constitution put forward by the opponents of the re - Islamization of the legal system of the North is in conflicts with some other sections of the Constitution that accord a special position to Shariah. Section 275 (1) of the 1999 Constitution provides that there shall be for any state that requires it, a Shariah Court of Appeal for that state. Section 275 (2) of the same constitution provides that the Shariah Court of Appeal shall consist of a Grand Kadi and such number of Kadis as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly of the state. The Governor of the state is empowered under section 276 (1) & (2) to appoint the Grand Kadis and the Kadis on the recommendation of the National Judicial Council. The appointment, in the case of the Grand Kadi is made subject to the confirmation of the House of Assembly of the state.

Section 276 (3) makes provisions for qualifications for appointment to the office of Kadi of the Shariah Court of Appeal of a state. According to the section:

(3) A person shall not be qualified to hold office as a Kadi of the Shariah Court of Appeal of a state unless:

(a) he is a legal practitioner in Nigeria and has been so qualified for a period of not less than ten years and has obtained a recognized qualification in Islamic Law from an institution acceptable to the National Judicial Council ; or

(b) he has attended and has obtained a recognized qualification in Islamic Law from an institution approved by the National Judicial Council and has held the qualification for a period of not less than ten years; and

i. he either has considerable experience in the practice of Islamic Law;

ii. he is a distinguished scholar of Islamic Law.

Section 277 (1) of the 1999 Constitution provides that the Shariah Court of Appeal shall in addition to such other jurisdiction as may be conferred upon it by the law of the state exercise such appellate and supervisory jurisdiction in civil proceedings involving questions of Islamic personal law which the court is competent to decide in accordance with the provisions of subsection (2) of this section.

Freedom of Religion as guaranteed in Section 38 (1) gives Muslims the right to practice their religion, which means to live according to Shariah According to the section:

(1) Every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom (either alone or in community with others, and in public or in private) to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice and observance.

Thirdly, the argument is that a state government lacks the constitutional power to enact Shariah laws in its territory lacks merit. To address this issue relating to the extent of the legislative powers of state governments vis - à - vis the Federation, we need to shift our focus to Section 4 of the Constitution under which the legislative powers in Nigeria are divided between the Federation and States. Part One of the Second Schedule of section 4 (2) specifies the exclusive legislative list on which only

the Federation may make laws while Part Two of the Second Schedule of section 4 (4) specifies the concurrent legislative list wherein the Federation and the States may make laws . States are empowered under section 7 of 1999 Constitution to make law on any other matter not mentioned in either of the lists. Since Penal law is not mentioned in either list, it is evident that this is the domain of state legislation. That been the case, a state has constitutional power to make law relating to Shariah Penal Code.

Again Section 6 of the Constitution empowers a State to establish Courts to exercise jurisdiction on matters with respect to which the House of Assembly of a State may make laws. It is axiomatic therefore that a state may establish a Shariah Criminal Court of first instance. Section 275 specifically empowers any state that requires it to establish its Shariah Court of Appeal to hear appeal from its lower Courts.

Moreover, Section 277 (1) stipulates that the state may confer on the courts any other jurisdiction. According to the supporters of Shariah, what this means is that the States are given the power to extend the jurisdiction of these courts to other domains , though Shariah opponents have argued that the wording of the beginning of Section 277 (2) ‘For the purposes of subsection (1) of this section , the Shariah Court of Appeal shall be competent to decide’ followed by various aspects of Islamic personal law restricts the meaning of subsection 1 and forbids the States from conferring other jurisdictions on the Shariah Courts of Appeal than matters of personal law²⁹.

Conflict with legislative prerogatives of the Federation

While it is evident that States had legislative competence to make penal law, it has been observed that some Shariah Penal Codes contain provisions with regard to

²⁹ Rudd Peter. Op. cit.

evidence³⁰, police and prisons which state legislation may not address as they fall within the exclusive legislative competence of the federal government³¹.

The Shariah law, as stated in the Quran, Hadith and other sources is not a "written law" within the meaning of Section 36 (12) of the 1999 Constitution. It was in an attempt to avoid the constitutional obstacle of this nature in the 1960 Constitution, on the application of Shariah that the Sardauna Regime caused one to be codified in 1960.

Under Section 36 (12) it is provided that:

“Subject as otherwise provided by this Constitution, a person shall not be convicted of a criminal offence unless that offence is defined and the penalty therein is prescribed in a written law, and in this subsection, a written law refers to an Act of the National Assembly or a Law of a State, any subsidiary legislation or instrument under the provisions of a law”.

That being the case, it is submitted that such sections in the Shariah penal codes making punishable any act or omission that is an offence under Shariah even if not mentioned in the penal code itself is unconstitutional³².

Shariah Penal Codes and Human Rights

Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution guarantees the fundamental rights of citizens. These rights are (1) right to life, (2) right to the dignity of human person (3) right to personal liberty (4) right to fair hearing (5) right to private and family life (6) right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion (7) right to freedom of expression and the press (8) right to peaceful assembly and association (9) right to freedom of movement

³⁰ See Kano Penal Code (section 127, explanation) Kebbi Penal Code (section 127) and Niger Penal Code (section 68A (3) (b) provides that four male witnesses are required to prove unlawful sexual intercourse

³¹ As appeared in the exclusive legislative list, there are certain domains related to penal law that are regarded as federal such as evidence (23) the police (45) and prison (48). State legislation cannot address these topics

³² See section 92 of Zamfara, Jigawa and Yobe penal codes. See also section 95 & section 93 of Bauchi and Kebbi penal codes.

(10) right to freedom from discrimination (11) and right to acquire and own immovable property anywhere in Nigeria.

Nigeria has also committed itself to guarantee basic human rights in various international contexts³³. The most important is the worldwide context within the framework of the United Nations. Nigeria has pledged to abide by the human rights standards within the framework of the Organisation of African Unity (The African Charter of Human and People's Right, (AACHPR) and of the Commonwealth. After the promulgation of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 which set standards for the human rights People's Rights, (ACHPR)) and of the Commonwealth. After the promulgation of the discourse, the United Nations has successfully formulated a number of international conventions in which human rights are further specified and made binding upon the signatories. Though sanctions on violations by the States parties are minimal, these conventions are significant in that they showed the commitment of the States parties. Some of these conventions of which Nigeria is a signatory are: The International Covenant on Civil and political Rights 1966 , the Convention For The Elimination Of All Forms Of Discrimination Against Women 1979, The Convention Against Torture And Other Cruel, Inhuman and Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984 (Henceforth CAT), And The Convention On The Rights Of The Child 1989.

Few jurists would deny that amputation of limbs and retaliation for grievous hurts such as blinding or the pulling out of teeth are indeed a form of torture. The same is the type of death by stoning and cruxification and certain instances of capital punishment in which the perpetrator is put to death in the same way as he killed the victim. If such punishments cannot be regarded as torture, then they certainly constitutes, inhuman or degrading punishment thus negating the 1999 constitution which provides in section 34 (1) (a) as follows:

“Every individual is entitled to respect for the dignity of his person and accordingly
(a) no person shall be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment.”

³³ Rudd Peter: Op. cit. at p. 37

But then it could be argued since Moslems to whom it applies believed that they were imposed by God through the Quran they could never be regarded as unlawful. And at any rate, restrictions under classical Shariah doctrine could be implored to render the application of these punishments extremely difficult. In some other Islamic countries where Islamic criminal law has been introduced, such as Pakistan, such mutilating punishments have not been carried out.

Another significant conflict between the Shariah and internationally recognized human rights in the Shariah is the provision that Muslims cannot change their religion and that if they do they face a death sentence. Apostasy (riddah) also entails the loss of civil rights such as the right to be married (the marriage of an Apostate is dissolved immediately) and the right to hold property.

Though none of the Penal Codes included apostasy as a punishable offence. This does not necessarily mean that apostasy cannot be punished under these laws since some of them provides that acts or omissions that are punishable crimes under the Shariah may be punished even in the absence of a provision in the Penal Codes. Since section 38 (1) of the 1999 Constitution ensures for everyone the rights to freedom, of thoughts, conscience and religion , including freedom to change his religion or belief, the offence of riddah is inconsistent with it, and by virtue of Section 1 (1) and (2) of the Constitution is unconstitutional . According to section of the 1999 constitution:

“(1) This Constitution is supreme and its provisions shall have binding force on all authorities and persons throughout the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

(2) If any other law is inconsistent with the provisions of the constitution, this constitution shall prevail and that other law shall to the extent of the inconsistency be void”.

We have in this paper attempted to examine the concept, sources and scope of Shariah examined the reintroduced Shariah Criminal Codes in the light of the 1999 Constitution on and locate its position within the context of the Nigerian legal system. We have also the enactment of Shariah Penal Codes is within the legislative competence of the states even the basis of which we are able to assert that

notwithstanding section 10 of the constitution, though these codes contains some provisions which are in direct conflict with the Nigerian Constitution such as provisions on evidence, police and prisons, (which are matters with federal legislative competence), mutilating and retaliatory punishments, apostasy, which is in conflict with the constitutional right to change one's religion. These offending provisions could either be abrogated by the state or struck out by the court applying the Blue Pencil Rule whenever opportunity to do so presents itself.

Conclusion

Shariah as a system of law is as much a religion inspired system as the Common Law and Equity which have been part of our legal system since the period of British Colonisation. If the reception of the English Common Law and Equity has not christianize the country despite being a Christian inspired system of law, then the reintroduction of Shariah penal code would not Islamise the country. It is submitted that adoption of Shariah penal code by some northern states to apply to their Moslems subjects does not amount to an attempt to make Islam the religion of that state. That the Common Law and Equity are Christian inspired system of law is supported by the dictum of Lord Summer's in *Bowman v. Secular Society Ltd*³⁴ to this effect:

“Ours is and always has been a Christian state. The English family is built on Christian ideas and if the national religion is not Christian there is none. English law may well be called a Christian law but we apply many of its rules and most of its principles, with equal justice and equally good government, in heathen communities and its sections, even in courts of conscience.”

This apart, every year the Assizes and the legal year are opened with church service wherein all judicial officers whether Muslims or Christians are required to attend such church services. Besides the Christian Sabbath (Sunday) is officially observed by all and sundry irrespective of faith and no Muslim has challenged these practices as

³⁴ Quoted in Quadri , Y.A. , Shariah : " The Islamic Way of Life " , the Seventh Ramadan Lecture organised by the University of Ibadan Muslim Community on 2nd January , 2000 , p . 27

imposition of Christian doctrine on the nation. It is therefore unfair and shows the highest level of intolerance on the part of Christians to complain of the adoption of Shariah by some Northern states which are predominantly Muslims particularly when no non-muslim is required to go to Shariah courts for litigation.

Antagonists of the Shariah have even condemned the Shariah provisions in the constitution as amounting to a dual legal system. Britain; in spite of her unitary political system has, alongside the English Law, the Scots Law whose origin and development differ from those of English law. Accordingly, Scotland has her own system of courts quite separate from and independent of the English Courts with the House of Lords as its final court of appeal. That being the case, we submit that there is nothing wrong or strange if Nigeria, a plural federal state should operate dual legal system. More so when Common Law and the Shariah have existed side by side in the country for more than a hundred years without any confusion.